

Why Sustainable Agriculture productivity is indispensable for World?

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After the 2nd World War, the world stepped into a new era in which agriculture production was boosted up by mechanization and chemical uses. All the developments placed their own significant marks on this society and environment in both ways positively and negatively. If we focus on the one side of the mirror the brighter one in which agricultural developments have positive aspects that raised the status of society, the economy of the world and feed the population of billions. Now if we go through the darker side these agricultural advances have left their footprints by decreasing the environmental quality (depletion of topsoil, air pollution, groundwater contamination, and greenhouse gasses production).

But to feed the billions of people is a hard job. Despite all the innovations and agricultural advances, there are millions of people that are in hunger and live under the threat of famine. If we go through the statistics of Pakistan, we will see some big figures but they are still not enough for the population of 22 crores. The agricultural sector contributes 18.9% of GDP and

42.3% of labour force is involved in it directly or indirectly. And Pakistan produces about 28 million tons of wheat but at the same time, Pakistan is at 92nd number out of 116 in the Global Hunger Index with a score of 24.7 which indicated a serious level of hunger. About 20% of Pakistani people are undernourished and 45% percent of children younger than five years of age are stunted. Now it's crucial for Pakistan to step forward towards sustainable agriculture, correlate with the world for sustainability, and feed this increasing population. According to the world bank, it is impossible to make a rise in economic growth, reduction in poverty, and hunger without making sustained progress in agriculture.

Now, here a question arises, how to move towards sustainable agriculture? Before this, we should understand what is sustainable agriculture. As we know we can't increase the area of this earth but our population is continuously increasing now, we have to increase our production from the same land but this time we have to feed more people without causing any

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damage to the soil, water, and environment to secure the future of next generations. In other words, Sustainability rests on the principle that we must meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

A transition towards sustainable agriculture is based on a series of small but realistic steps it's not an overnight process that we will use the magic pen and restore this earth. First of all, we have to secure our resources (like air, water, soil, and energy), and make sure of their efficient use of them. Then we have to improve our agricultural practices and take care of the market. Now it's necessary to move towards innovations that can help to work efficiently without harming the environment.

The goal of sustainable development is to strike a balance between our economic, environmental, and social demands, allowing us to succeed today and in the future. Sustainable development is a long-term, integrated strategy to grow and attain a healthy community by tackling economic, environmental, and social challenges together while avoiding excessive use of natural resources.

There are many other benefits that we will avail when we work for the sustainable agriculture. It will not only help to meet the needs of the future. But also make sure the effective use of land (according to classifications of lands and to get maximum benefits or production), conservation of environment (nourishes and restores the soil; conserve water resources), reducing greenhouse gases production, energy saving, reduces soil-water-air pollution, promotes local communities, and reducing costs of production & focus on profits.

Dedicated efforts are needed for sustainable agriculture. All the stakeholders (including youth and women, academia, researchers, rural communities, planners, policymakers and local institutions) should join hands towards a sustainable future.